

Falls Prevention on a Geriatric Female with Physiotherapy –Evidence Based Case Study Report

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Dr.S.S.Subramanian**, M.P.T (Orthopaedics), M.S (Education), M. Phil (Education), Ph.D (Physiotherapy).The Principal,Sree Balaji College Of physiotherapy,Chennai – 100. Affiliated To (Bharath) University, BIHER -Chennai – 73. ⁽²⁾**M.SINDHUJA RAJESH.,B.P.T.,MIAP**-Tutor in Physiotherapy-Sree Balaji College Of physiotherapy, Chennai – 100. Affiliated To (Bharath) University, BIHER Chennai – 73.⁽³⁾**Hema. S** ⁽⁴⁾**Saranya Devi**. M- III Year, B.P.T students Sree Balaji College of Physiotherapy. Bharath University, Chennai-100

Abstract:

Evidenced with an increasing longevity globally, especially in India health, care needs to strengthened among geriatric population. Various factors such as pain, obesity, decreased balance, living alone, effect of medication, osteoporosis can lead to fall which can devastate life of elderly.

Aims and objective: *This original case study strives to evaluate the efficacy of physiotherapy on falls prevention means of, with clinical and functional prognosis of this subject.*

Materials and methodology: *Specific strengthening, core and proprioceptive exercises were used with a weekly twice frequency. The subject was treated for each session with 25-30 minutes duration of exercises, during the period from October 2016 to march 2017.*

Results: *Pre and post mors falls prevention scale were evaluated and a 3 fold decrease in the risk for fall was recorded.*

Conclusion: *As the subject has benefited against fall by specific non- pharmacological means with physical exercises, the outcome of the study has pointed with huge impact on not only falls prevention, but an improved confidence and even enhanced quality of life of the study subject, hence evidencing specific physical therapy measures of more beneficial among elders.*

Keywords: *Morse falls scale, Geriatric, BMI – Body Mass Index, IADL- instrumental activities of dailylife, PRT – Progressive resisted training*

INTRODUCTION:

Worldwide the average life span of people has been increasing with several factors including hereditary, life style, and healthy diet. WHO reports 600 million elderly individuals worldwide, and India has 9 % geriatric population (Census 2011)

Factors associated with fear of falling includes: Older age, Being female Previous falls Resulting associate fracture with fear of falling Decreased mobility Poor balance Chronic dizziness Higher level of pain Living alone Restricted instrumental ADL (Gagnon et al 2003) .

Osteoporosis may result in low impact or spontaneous fragility fractures which can lead to a fall (TR miller et al 2006). Women were predisposed to falls (Schwartz et al 2002) .Subjects with osteoporotic bones, be at a greater risk of injury (Wark JD 1996). Risk factors for falling could be fear of falling which cause activity restriction, leading to muscle atrophy, reduced health and physical functioning (Tinetti 1988) can compromise quality of life, such as limiting social contacts or leisure activities (Arken et al 1994). The importance of identifying specific risk factors and the value of multidisciplinary assessment of patients who fall are increasingly being recognized (Chang et al 2004). Falls in older people place heavy demands on health care system (Rivara and Wolf 1992) and interventions that target the risk factors contributing to falls are highly recommended (National Service Framework, UK, 2001)

About 30 % of people over 65 yrs of age fall each year and the incidence of falls over 75 yrs of age is 32 – 42 % (Tinetti and Speecheley 1989). Falls are the leading cause of hospitalization and injury related death in persons 75 yrs and older (Gillespie et al 2003). The prevention of falls is therefore important to reduce morbidity and mortality among geriatric population. Falls are a major cause of disability and preventable cause of death in older people (Lin et al 2007) . Physical exercise program may be effective in improving balance, mobility and postural stability to decrease fall risk.(Pata et al 2013.)

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

- i. To analyze the efficacy of specific physiotherapy means on falls prevention (morse falls scale).
- ii. To evaluate the clinical prognosis with physiotherapy

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

PAST MEDICAL HISTORY:

75 yrs old widow, graduate, living alone, known hypersensitive on T.Etilaal and T.penlin; BMI – 32 kg / metresquare, waist circumference – 113 cm, bilateral genu recurvatum, antalgic gait .C/o falls frequently since Jan 2016 and increased fear of falling .Tool used: Morse falls scale for fall risk factors on a 2 point scale of 6 items.Design: case control study .Duration of the study: October 2016 to March 2017. With fear of falling this widow living alone in a bunglow in southern India was dependant on a paid care giver for walking (in open environment) and for social activities, hence her musculoskeletal ailments, anxiety and depression were increasing. So with multiple factors for falling she was attending physiotherapy department for prevention of falls and to improve her quality of lie as major objective .After due explanation and got her consent for this study, author has started specific physiotherapy means as mentioned below:

Treatment used: Balanced exercises, Proprioceptive training, strengthening of core muscles. Frequency of weekly twice for 25-30minutes, home programme includes walking with monitoring for 20 minutess daily and a set of exercises.

RESULT:

Clinical prognosis of the subject:

An improved level of self-confidence, to walk regularly for 15-20 minutes.An enhanced physical functioning which includes digestion, bladder bowel movements, reduction in bilateral knee and low back pain. She has started attending social and spiritual activities which she was not doing since 2 years as with fear of falling. Also last year with monthly 2-3fall reported by her, this 6months study period she had fallen once within her residence. She has started her regular walking and home programme of few exercises with improved faith, and confidence as evidenced with her enhanced quality of life.

Table of results on pre and post morse scale on the subject:

TEST	MORSE FALLS SCALE %
PRE	50
POST	15

MORSE FALLS SCALE: 6 ITEMS RELATED TO FALLRISK FACTORS ON A 2 POINT SCALE Note: more than >45 was high risk>25 low risk

DISCUSSION:

This study subject has benefited with physiotherapy with reduced risk of falling as inferred from the above table as from being a high risk subject to a low risk category for falls.

Balance training is an essential component of fall prevention program (Hakim et al 2004) and this Subjects was treated with specific exercises in sitting and standing for to improve balance.

Progressive resisted training was effective in improving balance (Joshwa et al 2014) in an Mangalore based study on 54 elderly subjects in concurrence with this study. This study subject was treated with resisted exercises and core exercises using Physioball.

With strengthening of muscles in geriatric subjects an improved muscle strength, mass, composition, power, torque production and modification of mechanical properties of tendon (Reeves et al 2016) strengthening exercises as used on his subject has above said benefits.

(vogler et al 2009) have among older adults in a 12 week study have recorded an improved reaction time with weight bearing exercises, this subject was treated with proprioceptive exercises.

Uniqueness of this study: Perception even among health care providers on physiotherapy was mainly alleviation of pain, mobilize joints following injury and strengthen weak muscles, but an unfocused areas of various therapeutic tools such as core strengthening, proprioception were applied on this subject and reasonable prognosis, recorded was unique with the study

Limitations of this original research study was being a case study of shorter duration and only a variable subjective rating scale was used further studies of larger sample size, longer duration including subjects of both sex and more variables are recommended.

Conclusion:

Geriatric physiotherapy, an emerging arena, where comprehensive therapeutic ways needs a long way to go for research perspective. Hence this original study brings more emphasis on specific physical therapy for increasing elderly populations wellbeing.

As elderly subjects with due physiotherapy intervention, falls can be prevented, helps to improve self-confidence and enhance their quality of life is evidence from this study findings.

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